

**ROLE OF NABARD FOR MICRO FINANCE PROMOTION AND PROBLEMS –
CHALLENGES OF MICRO FINANCE ENTREPRENEUR AND MICRO FINANCE
INSTITUTIONS**

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ABSTRACT

Micro-finance is an innovative credit delivery mechanism that ensures viable financial services for the needy. The Government of India widens the micro-credit reach for the million poor in India through the self-employment scheme. The National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development Bank (NABARD) envisages reaching banking services to one-third of the very poor in India, that is a population of about 100 million rural poor through one million self-help groups (SHGs) by 2007-08. All domestic commercial banks are required to allocate 40% of their lending to the priority sectors, such as, SHGs, Micro-finance institution (MFIs) and Regional Rural Banks and allied activities. Compared to return on government bonds of 6-7%, MFI lending provided returns of 10-14%. Banks therefore, have expanded investments in these areas. This paper discusses the initiatives of NABARD in promoting micro-finance and emphasizes is given on problem and challenges of micro-entrepreneurs n micro-finance institutions and efforts were also made to suggest remedial measures to improve micro-finance in the light of the study.

Keywords: Microfinance, NABARD Initiatives, MFE, MFI

1. INTRODUCTION

In the early 1900s, various micro-finance programmes began to appear in the parts of rural Latin America. These banks were owned by the government and other private banks. Between 1950s and 1970s, government and donors focused on providing agricultural credit to

small and marginal farmers. These efforts to expand access to agricultural credit emphasized supply led government interventions in the form of targeted credit through state owned development finance institutions to customer at below market interest rates. Meanwhile, starting in the 1970s experimental programs in Bangladesh, Brazil and a few other countries extended tiny loans to groups of poor women to invest in micro-business.

The field of micro-finance has grown in size and status since its humble origin 1976 in Bangladesh. The announcement of 2006 noble peace prize award to Prof. Mohammed Yunus, originator of micro-finance, and Grameena Bank, the institution he founded, marks a significant milestone in the recognition of the field of micro-finance by the international community.

In the developing countries like India, where majority of the population resides in rural areas, rural development becomes imperative for the economic development of that nation and for the rural development. As a result, micro-finance services have grown rapidly during the last decades. About 95% poor households in India still have little access to institutional financial services.

In the regard the financing of small and medium enterprises have drawn the attention of several financial institutions. The National Banks for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) has emerged as a pioneer in the field of micro-finance, thereby ensuring financial inclusion for more than 5.8 crores households within its folds.

In order to improve access of the poor to formal poor banking, NABARD launched self-help groups (SHG) Banks linkages model in 1992. Under this scheme the poor form small groups and are encouraged to poor their savings regularly. These savings are then used to make small interest-bearing loans to members. Banks credit follows this stage.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To know the concepts of micro-finance.
2. To know the NABARD initiatives in programming micro-finance.
3. To know the problems – challenges of MFEs.
4. To know the problems-challenges of MFIs.

3. METHADODOLOGY

The study is purely based on secondary data. The relevant secondary data are collected from the different authorized websites, reports, textbooks and journals

CONCEPT OF MICRO-FINANCE

As the name suggests, micro-finance is the provision of financial services (Loans, savings, insurance) to people on a small scale, such as business with low or moderate incomes, but you can read more meticulous definition here and here loans of micro values are one of the better-known means of helping small business owners in developing countries move out of poverty.

The definition for according to the Asian Development Banks (ADB) is any financial service targeted towards the poor such as,

- Deposits.
- Finance scheme or loans upto \$3000.
- Payment services.
- Money transfers.
- Insurance to poor and low-income households and their micro-enterprises.

As Kofi Annan once put it, micro-finance not only recognizes the needs of the poor, it also empowers them and taps into their remarkable reservoir of energy and knowledge. In short, micro-finance has tremendous potential, its time is now and is here to stay.

NEED FOR MICRO CREDIT

The limitations of formal financial sector in extending credit to the beneficiaries for assuring employment opportunities led to the evolution of the programme of micro credit with the objective of providing poor timely and hassle-free credit without demanding any collateral.

The harmony among the group members cohesiveness in the group followed by group pressure in determining repayment schedule and ensuring prompt and faultless repayment, supervision of co-borrower's activities in the system are the important aspects of the micro-credit.

SOURCES OF MICRO-FINANCE

Micro-finance providers come in various forms which can be broadly grouped as follows.

- 1) Formal micro-finance Institutions rural/micro-finance/village banks, commercial banks, telecom firms, and co-operative offering loans to lower income group individuals.
- 2) Semi-formal micro-finance institutions non-government organizations providing micro-sized loans.
- 3) Informal micro-finance source money lenders and shopkeepers who often loan money on a daily basis and charge exorbitant interest rates.

NABARD INITIATIVES FOR MICRO-FINANCE PROMOTION

NABARD has initiated several measures for the healthy growth of the SHG linkage programme. Viz

- 1) Developing conducive policy frame work through the provision of opening savings banks accounts in the names of SHGs.
- 2) Relaxation of collateral norms.
- 3) Simple documentation and delegation credit decisions to SHGs.
- 4) Training and awareness building among the stakeholders.
- 5) Encouraging RRRBs and co-operative banks to act as SHGs promoting institutions.
- 6) To provide support to NGO's for promoting of SHGs etc.

SHG- BANK LINKAGE SCHEME

Against this background, a need was felt for supplementary policies, systems and procedures, savings and loan products, other complementary services, and new delivery mechanism which would fulfill the requirements of the poor, especially of the women members of such households. The launching of NABARD's pilot phase of the SHG (Self Help Group) Bank linkage programme in February 1992 can be considered as a landmark development in the banking with the poor. The SHG informal thrift and credit groups of poor came to be recognized as bank clients under the pilot phase. The strategy induced was simple, viz. forming small, cohesive and participative groups of the poor, encouraging them to the poor their thrift regularly and using the pooled thrift to make small interest-bearing loans to members, and in the process of learning the nuances of financial discipline.

PROMOTIONAL SUPPORT-SHG-BANK-LINKAGE

1) MICRO FIANCE DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY FUND (MFDEF)

Recognizing the need for upscaling the micro-finance interventions in the country, the Hon'ble Union Finance Minister, while presenting the budget for the year 2000-01, announced the creation of a Micro Finance development Fund (MFDF) with initial contribution o Rs. 1 billion, to be funded by Reserve Bank of India and NABARD (Rs. 400 million each) and the Rs. 200 million to be contributed by the commercial banks. In the Union Budget for 2005-06, the Government of India had decided to re-designate the existing MFDF as Micro Finance Development and Equity Fund (MFDEF) and raised its corpus from Rs. 1 billion to Rs. 2 billion with the similar ratio of contributions. The MFDEF is managed and administered by NABARD.

The major components of the assistance include promotional grant assistance of Self-Help Promoting Agencies, training and capacity building for microfinance clients and stakeholders of SHG-Bank Linkage Programme, funding support to MFIs, Management Information System (MIS) for microfinance, research. Studies and publication.

2) GRANT SUPPORT TO PARTNER AGENCIES FOR PROMOTION AND NURTURING OF SHGs

NABARD has been instrumental in the formation and nurturing of quality SHGs by means of promotional grant support to NGOs, RRBs, DCCBs, Farmer's Club's and Individual Rural Volunteers and by facilitating capacity building of various partners, which has brought excellent results in the promotion and credit linkage of SHGs. Further, the number of partner institutions functioning as Self-Help Promoting Institutions (SHPIs) over the years has increased to 2592, which has resulted in the expansion of the programme throughout the country.

3) PILOT PROJECT ON SHG-POST OFFICE LINKAGE PROGRAMME

The Pilot Project for SHG-Post Office Linkage programme was initially launched in 5 select districts of Tamil Nadu, viz, Sivaganga, Pudukottai, Tiruvannamalai, Thanjavur and Tiruvarur with the objective of examining the feasibility of utilizing the vast network of Post Offices in rural areas in disbursement of credit to rural poor, through SHGs, on agency basis. The progress under the project has been encouraging. As on 31st March 2009, 2,835 SHGs have opened zero interest savings accounts with select Post Offices in Tamilnadu and 889 SHGs have been credit linked with loan amounting to Rs. 21.3 million.

SPECIAL INITIATIVES IN BACKWARD REGION

1) RAJIV GANDHI MAHILA VIKAS PARIYOJANA (RGMVP)

NABARD continued to support the RGMVP, a special initiative of Rajiv Gandhi Charitable Trust (RGCT) for promotion, credit linkage and federation of SHGs, in select district of UP with participating banks and implementing NGOs. With an implementation period of eight years (2007-2014) the project covers 15 Blocks in Phase 1 and 29 blocks in Phase 2. An amount of Rs. 50.9 million and Rs. 110.3 million has been sanctioned for Phase 1 and Phase 2, respectively.

2) PRIYADARSHINI PROJECT

A Programme for 'Rural Women Empowerment and Livelihood in Mid- Gangetic Plains' called "Priyadarshini" envisaging holistic empowerment of 1, 08, 000 poor women and adolescent girls through formation of 7200 SHGs was launched on 4th December 2009. This is

covered in four districts (Sultanpur, Banraich, Shravasti and Rae Bareilly of Uttar Pradesh and two districts (Madhubani and Sitamarhi) of Bihar.

3) WATERSHED DEVELOPMENT

In pursuance of the Union Finance Minister's budget speech for 1999-2000 a Watershed Development Fund (WDF) has been created in NABARD with a contribution of Rs 1 billion each by MoA, Government of India and NABARD. Watershed development covers the conservation, regeneration, and the judicious use of human and natural (like land, water, plants, animals) resources within a particular watershed. It requires people's participation because conservation is possible only through the whole-hearted involvement of the entire community.

4) WADI MODEL

The implementation of Comprehensive Adivasi Development Programmes (ADPs) in Gujjer AINXW 1995 and in Maharashtra since 2000 had provided several insights for NABARD in framing strategies for holistic development of tribal regions, The ADP were externally supported by German bank-KfW who have chosen NABARD as Indian partner and the central focus of the ADPs is "wadi" (small orchard) together with suitable soil conservation, water resource development measures and other measures for improving the quality of tribal life such as community health & sanitation, women development, institution development etc.

PROBLEMS –CHALLENGES OF MICRO-FINANCE ENTERPRENUER

Although the importance of micro finance in the process of poverty eradication is realized, it faces multiple problems. Offering financed services to the poor individual is a complex process and that in itself leads to various challenges.

1) The poor inability to offer marketable collateral for loans

Micro-finance clients are either very small business or poor individual who usually have few assets, non-existent credit histories and low-income levels. This becomes big problem it means these clients are unable to produce required collateral to MFI against loans and thus are excluded from the services.

2) Poor Institutional viability of micro-entrepreneurs

Poorly constructed business ideas with limited amount of capital and lack of consideration of demand and costs render the micro venture unsustainable, and micro finance may incorrectly get the blame for it. For instance, in the case of micro-crop farming, farmers often fail to account for their personal consumption between sowing and harvesting periods and

realize they face shortage of money. As a result, they often end-up using the loan for personal matters. The problem arises when its time to repay the loan. The farmer is no other way's and forced to take up second loan to repay the original loan. This may lead to vicious cycle where the farmers get inundated with debt.

3) Lack of knowledge about micro finance services

Many micro entrepreneurs live in for off rural areas, unaware of the micro finance services leads to little access to micro-finance offered by MFI.

4) Shortage of financial capital or misallocation

One of the severe problems arises for entrepreneur a lack of funds. Without credit, the micro ventures may not grow or quickly take advantage of opportunities. Since, 20% of the worlds population accounts for 86% of consumption one can deduce that problem is not to the shortage, but rather misallocation of funds.

5) Inability to exploit growth opportunities.

The remote locations of micro-business mean they have little information pertaining to their markets, such as customer needs and competitors' strengths and weakness and so on. As a result, many critics may find faults with the idea of micro-finance, not realizing that this is not a really a problem, but just a challenge that can be overcome as business grows increases its capital base.

6) Few organizational resource and poor governance

Micro entrepreneur has limited skills, qualifications and exposure to handling business. While they need to be trained through capacity building initiatives by the MFI, many micro entrepreneurs may not grow as planned because of these problems for insurance, they may borrow more money than needed, or misallocate it in their business and end up bearing the burden of large interest payments instead of enjoying the fruits of their business.

7) Low bargaining power

Micro entrepreneur is scattered over different parts of the country and moreover they are not well organized. So collective bargaining is not possible and today's market are competitive markets because of their small size their individual bargaining power is determined when dealing with customers. However, at the other spectrum, there still is not any respite because micro entrepreneurs deal with MFIs on an individual basis, which also erodes their bargaining power. This is not really a problem for micro-finance, bur rather micro entrepreneurs.

8) Vulnerability to economic shocks.

Micro-entrepreneur is not so strong to face economic shocks susceptible to sudden change in customer demand because, their business cannot sustain losses owing to their small size (low capital) which may lead to non-payments of loan micro entrepreneur becomes the defaulter.

PROBLEMS-CHALLENGES OF MICRO FINANCE INSTITUTIONS

1) Perceived high risk of micro entrepreneurship and small business.

Micro-entrepreneur is poor and unable to offer collateral to micro-finance providers against loans, they usually lack an alternate source of income, and have little, if any, formal education or training in the areas of their business. As a result, commercial banks attribute a high credit risk to micro-entrepreneurs and steer clear of this sector. This becomes initial problems of MFI.

2) High court involved in small transactions micro lending.

The small size of micro entrepreneur increases the transaction costs for MFIs because they cannot process loans in bulk. This denies MFIs the benefits of economic of scale. Hence, they are forced to cover their costs through high interest rates on loans.

3) Lack of Debt and Equity Funds for MFIs to pass on to the poor.

Capital availability for micro finance is hardly a problem owing to the rapid growth in the micro finance sectors, which has been fueled by the attention from the media and development agencies. Even though there are plenty of finance options available for MFIs there is an emerging shortage of money because of the current financial crises across the globe. Another reasons for this shortfall are the lack of awareness of funding sources by MFI managers.

4) Difficulty in measuring the social performance of MFIs.

Micro finance is delivering the economic returns its propents promise, but there are only a handful of tools available that measures the social returns of the loan programs for the poor. To add the problem, the tools use proxies to estimate the amount of poverty and social change surrounding micro entrepreneurs. This makes the gathering of funds a challenge because donors may question the actual impact made by micro-finance.

5) Mixing charity with business.

Since credit without strict discipline is nothing but charity (Professor Yunus), if microfinance providers fail to protect themselves against loan delinquency, they will, in effect, prioritize social objective at the expenses of financial sustainability. Improper delinquency management is a result of inadequate implementation of corporate governance principles, and formal as well as semi-formal microfinance providers often suffer this. As a result, looser controls over microfinance deals will lead to higher default rates.

6) Lack of Customized Solutions for the Poor.

Inappropriate targeting of poor households by micro finance programs is a common problem because MFIs fail to understand the varied needs of micro entrepreneurs. MFIs must spend time in the field with their clients and his/ her business, and then use this research to develop customized microfinance tools for each micro entrepreneur.

Generalized solutions may work for the large companies dealing with large homogenous customer groups, but micro finance providers need to serve the varied needs of individuals in each micro market segment.

7) Lack of micro-finance training for human resource in micro-finance institution

Working in the microfinance sector is a different ball game compared to the traditional financial sector. For instance, micro-finance officers and volunteers need to talk a different language, build lasting relationships with individual micro entrepreneurs, understand the unique needs of the poor, evaluate the borrower's sustainability, and grasp the cultural nuances of the borrower's communities. It's no surprise microfinance providers need special training to ensure they avoid problems such as intimidating or under-serving clients.

8) Poor distribution system of micro-finance institutions and lack of information about microfinance investment opportunities

There are over 10,000 MFIs across the world, but their reach is only 4% of the potential market. World Bank, 2001. This is a slight problem because even though there are over 10,000 MFIs around the world, they may not know about the existence and needs of certain micro entrepreneurs.

9) Dual mission of Microfinance Institutions to be Financially Sustainable as well as Development Oriented

Micro finance tends to forget their objective is social development and not profit creation. The principle of ‘one micro entrepreneur –one micro loan’ is overlooked by profit –hungry MFIs who end up targeting the same individual for many loans and causes multiple borrowing (also known as credit population). This is a major problem because at the end of the day, that individual get burdened by mounting interest payments and is pushed deeper into the folds of poverty. Poor governance on the side of MFIs as well as the micro entrepreneur are to blame for this.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The study shows that NABARD participation in rural development during the last 25 years have been silver lining on the rural horizon and many initiatives have taken for uplifting rural mass to improve their standard of living. And it is observed that Micro-entrepreneur problems are caused by their small size, varied location and lack of skill etc. And microfinance institutions have to run under strict rules and regulations and little bit time is needed to correct all the problems despite these problems; the prospects of micro finance are quite bright in near future.

The following suggestion are considered for reconstruction and smooth running of micro-finance. They are

- 1) Co-operative attitude and whole hearted advice and tutoring of bank staff can bring success to micro-entrepreneur.
- 2) Evening business hours is to be introduced on experimental basis it will help the rural people to reap maximum benefit of micro-finance.
- 3) The government has to come forward and make an arrangement of trade fairs exhibitions to SHG members would be much benefited.
- 4) To provide extensive co-operative education and training at village level through integrated approach of adult education in rural areas to MFE.

There shall be an open and co-operative relationship between MFI and MFE.

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